

Synthesis and characterization of proton exchange membrane prepared from poly(phenylene oxide) and poly(vinyl alcohol)[†]

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Abstract : We report the synthesis of a new proton-conducting polymer membrane using poly(vinyl alcohol) and poly(phenylene oxide) (PPO). Sulfonated PPO was synthesized by direct sulfonation using chlorosulfonic acid as the sulfonating reagent. The sulfonated PPO (sPPO)-poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) membranes were prepared in different ratios. To assess the membrane performance the following characterizations were carried out : ion-exchange capacities, water uptakes, transport numbers, water-diffusion coefficients, and conductivities. The thermal decomposition of poly(vinyl alcohol)-sulfonated poly(phenylene oxide) (PVA-sPPO) membranes was similar to be the pure sPPO membrane. Proton conductivities of PVA-sPPO membranes increased with increasing sulfonation content and the conductivity value of the PVA-sPPO 70 membrane was 0.0092 S cm⁻¹. The membrane potential sPPO-PVA 70 membrane was 57 mV at 0.00625 N HCl which compared favourably to other sPPO-PVA membranes. The transport number of sPPO-PVA 70 was 0.97. Overall, the sPPO-PVA 70 exhibited very good properties when compared to other sPPO-PVA membranes.

Keywords : Proton exchange membrane, poly(phenylene oxide), poly(vinyl alcohol), sulphonation, membrane potential.

Introduction

For decades, perfluorinated membranes such as Nafion (a copolymer of tetrafluoroethylene and sulfonyl fluoride vinyl ether developed by DuPont), have been the benchmark in electrodialysis, and recently in the proton exchange fuel cell industry. The excellent proton conductivity (about 0.1 S cm⁻¹) of this membrane is due to the presence of the most electronegative atom, fluorine, and the attached sulfonic acid groups. Their high mechanical strength and thermal stability is due to presence of a poly(tetrafluoroethylene)-like backbone¹. Nafion also possesses very good chemical stability in the highly oxidative and reductive environments encountered in electrodialysis or fuel cell applications. In addition to the benefits mentioned above, there are also some drawbacks. As a fluorinated material, the manufacturing process is not environmentally-friendly, and requires a high level

of safety, as well as complicated processing steps resulting in a prohibitively high cost for large scale applications²⁻⁷. Heat and water management issues also occur with membranes that require sufficient and uniform water to achieve the best performance in proton exchange membrane fuel cells.

In response to the challenges above, the modification of cheaper and conventional arylene main-chain polymers has given rise to a large scope of research and development into novel non-fluorinated membranes that would possess the desired properties but still be affordable and environment-friendly.

Sulfonation is the most common method to convert hydrophobic polymers into hydrophilic species, making them capable of proton and water transportation. The obtained sulfonated material may be blended with a suitable polymer to provide the film/membrane-forming pro-

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

perty and requisite strength. Covalent cross-linking of blended membranes can give them stability in aqueous environments. Notable polymers that have been sulfonated include poly(sulfone), poly(ethersulfone), poly(ether ether ketone), poly(imidazole), poly(benzimidazole), poly(phenylene) and poly(phenylene oxide). These membranes can be prepared by blending, covalent cross-linking and ionic cross-linking⁸⁻¹⁵. Poly(vinyl alcohol) has been used as a common blending agent because of its excellent flexible membrane characteristics and hydrophobic properties. Developments in ion-exchange membranes and electrochemical processes prior to 2005 have been summarized by Nagarale *et al.*¹⁶, and a review on organic-inorganic composite membranes has also been presented by Nagarale *et al.*¹⁷.

In our study, we have sulfonated poly(phenylene oxide) with chlorosulfonic acid and prepared various blends of poly(vinyl alcohol) having different compositions. The prepared membranes were studied for their performance and related electro-chemical properties, and tested for their mechanical and thermal stabilities. The choice of poly(phenylene oxide) as a base material was due to its excellent membrane-forming property and chemical stability in an oxidative environment (due to the presence of inherent oxygen). Another advantage observed was its quick (1–2 h) sulfonation reaction under room temperature conditions (25–30 °C) with no requirement for the special provision of an inert atmosphere, thus offering ease of processing.

Experimental

Materials :

2,6-Dimethyl-1,4-phenylene oxide (FW 138.2, Sigma-Aldrich), chloroform (Ranbaxy, India), chlorosulfonic acid (Loba Chemie), poly(vinyl alcohol) (87–89% hydrolysed, Sigma-Aldrich), acetone (Ranbaxy), glutaraldehyde (25% aqueous, Loba Chemie), sulfuric acid (98%, Ranbaxy), sodium hydroxide (AR grade, Fisher Scientific), hydrochloric acid (36% min, Fisher Scientific), diethyl ether (Loba Chemie), Nafion 115 (DuPont), water (deionized, Millipore).

Membrane preparation :

Sulfonation of poly(phenylene oxide) :

Oven-dried 2,6-dimethyl-1,4-phenylene oxide (PPO)

was dissolved in chloroform at room temperature to form a 3% solution. Chlorosulfonic acid (5% solution in chloroform) was added to slowly to the polymer solution with stirring, at room temperature, until the sulfonated PPO (sPPO) precipitated completely¹⁸. The precipitated material was isolated and washed first with diethyl ether, then with demineralised water, and kept soaked in aqueous ammonia overnight. It was again washed with water until the pH value reached about 7.0, and dried in oven at 40 °C for 24 h.

Membrane casting :

Pure sPPO did not form a flexible membrane and experiences excessive swelling in water, and was therefore considered a suitable candidate for blending with PVA. Different compositions of sPPO-PVA membrane were prepared by dissolving the required amounts of sPPO in a PVA solution (5% in dimethyl acetamide (DMAc)). The consistency of the casting solution was adjusted to enable uniform spreading over horizontal polyester sheets when poured. As an alternative method, a manually operated casting knife was used. The casted solution was allowed to dry under room conditions for 24 h to obtain dense membranes and then transferred to a 40 °C oven for further drying. Prepared membranes were further cross-linked by 30 min immersion in an acetone solution comprising a cross-linking agent, glutaraldehyde (0.1 mol L⁻¹), and acid catalyst, sulfuric acid (0.01 mol L⁻¹), at 30 °C in a water bath. After several trials, a suitable duration for the cross-linking reaction was determined as 30 min. This ensured that the membrane remained stable (i.e. possessed sufficient working strength in 80 °C water) and did not leach out. Prior to characterization, cross-linked membranes were pre-treated by 3 cycles of alternative soaking in 0.1 N HCl and 0.1 N NaOH for 1 h, and then preserved in deionized water. Based on the sulfonation concentration, the membranes were coded as poly(vinyl alcohol)-sulfonated poly(phenylene oxide) PVA-sPPO 30, 40, 50, 60, and 70.

Membrane characterization :

Using a digital screw gauge (Forbes Gokak, India), the thickness of sPPO-PVA membranes of various sPPO and PVA ratios was measured in the ranges of 80–100 microns for dry membranes and 100–140 microns for wet membranes at different locations of the membrane

surface. An average value was used for calculations.

Water uptake :

Membrane water uptake was measured using an automatic moisture balance (Citizen MBC 50) equipped with an IR/halogen lamp that heated the sample up to 120 °C before auto switch-off. Membrane samples were immersed for a minimum of 12 h in water at the specified temperature. Surface water was removed from the samples using filter paper, and they were immediately transferred to the pan and heated. Dynamic measurements were displayed as the reduction in weight due to evaporation of water took place and the final results were recorded when no more moisture was removed at 120 °C.

The percentage water uptake by the membrane (%W) is given as

$$\%W = \frac{W_{\text{wet}} - W_{\text{dry}}}{W_{\text{dry}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The % volume of water (% ϕ_w) in a wet membrane was estimated from the following equation¹⁹.

$$\begin{aligned} \% \phi_w &= \frac{\text{Water volume}}{\text{Water volume} + \text{Polymer volume}} \times 100 \\ &= \frac{(W_{\text{wet}} - W_{\text{dry}})/\rho_w}{(W_{\text{wet}} - W_{\text{dry}})/\rho_w + (W_{\text{dry}}/\rho_p)} \times 100 \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

where W_{wet} and W_{dry} are the wet and dry weights of membrane, and ρ_w and ρ_p are the densities of water and polymer respectively.

Ion exchange capacity (IEC) :

IEC of sPPO-PVA membranes was estimated by acidimetric titration. To protonate the membranes, weighed samples were immersed in 0.1 N HCl for at least 6 h, washed completely with water and then soaked in 2 M NaCl solution for a minimum 12 h at room temperature. The membranes were removed and the amount of HCl formed in NaCl due to ion exchange was measured by titrating NaCl solution against 0.01 N NaOH in the presence of the indicator phenolphthalein. IEC (milliequivalents of $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}^-$ group per unit dry weight of polymer) was calculated as :

$$IEC = \frac{NV}{W_{\text{dry}}} \quad (3)$$

where N is normality and V is volume of NaOH solution used.

Transport number :

Transport number was estimated by the measurement of membrane potential using a lab-fabricated two-compartment cell²⁰. A circular piece of membrane was equilibrated in an electrolyte solution at the specified temperature and was placed between the two halves of the cell that were filled with electrolyte solutions of different concentrations and ionically connected with an agar-agar-KCl salt bridge. For all measurements, $C_1/C_2 = 10$ and $\Delta C/C_{\text{mean}} = 1.60$, where C_1 and C_2 are electrolyte concentrations, $\Delta C = C_1 - C_2$ and $C_{\text{mean}} = (C_1 + C_2)/2$. The solutions were kept well stirred with magnetic stirrers and the potential difference developed between two sides of the membrane near its surface, due to migration of protons through the membrane, was recorded using a digital multimeter with a resolution of 0.1 mV.

Membrane conductivity :

Membrane conductivity was estimated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy²¹⁻²³ using Autolab (Metrohm) apparatus at room (30 °C) as well as at elevated temperature (40–80 °C). The two probe method was used to determine through plane conductivities. Measurements were performed in potentiostatic mode with a sinusoidal signal applied to a lab-manufactured two-compartment cylindrical cell placing the circular membrane inside that was immersed in sulphuric acid electrolyte at both sides between two graphite electrodes. When the two halves of the cell were tightened with a C-clamp, the smoothly machined circular graphite electrodes with a surface area of 1.5 cm² were 1.05-cm apart. Electrolyte (~1.7 mL) was introduced with a syringe into each compartment after closing the cell and taking care that no air bubbles were trapped.

For elevated temperature measurements the cell was kept inside a wooden cabinet with the capability of maintaining a set temperature. Hot solution was introduced into the cell after equilibration with the outside temperature so that solution did not cool during the measurement. Data analysis was performed using NOVA 1.6 software supplied with the instrument.

Thermal stability :

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were performed

for evaluating the thermal stability of synthesized sulfonated material i.e. sPPO, in the atmosphere. The apparatus consisted of a 4 decimal digital balance (Afcoset, sensitivity 0.1 mg), a temperature controller (Indotherm, Model MPC 500), a power regulator (Indotherm, 3 kVA), a chromel-alumel thermocouple, and a furnace. The software (RsCom Ver. 2.40) for recording data was supplied by A & D Company Ltd. The samples were heated from room temperature to about 550 °C with a heating rate of 4 °C min⁻¹. Sample weights were recorded in dynamic mode with increasing temperature until the entire material had disappeared or very little (less than 5%) residue was left.

Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) :

FTIR (with a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 2 in the wavelength range 400–4000 cm⁻¹) was used to confirm the attached sulfonic acid group in sPPO. Spectra were obtained for pure PPO, sulfonated PPO and sPPO-PVA membrane and compared. A strong peak appeared at 1030 cm⁻¹, which corresponded to the sulfonic acid group.

Proton NMR :

Proton NMR was recorded by in DMSO for sPPO and in deuteriochloroform (Chloroform-D, Aldrich) for PPO using a Jeol 500 MHz NMR and degree of sulfonation was estimated.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) :

SEM revealed the phase separation of the membranes showing the hydrophilic and hydrophobic domains. The images were obtained via SEM (Carl Zeiss, Model Supra 40 VP, Germany). Since the samples were electrically insulated, a gold coating of thickness 10–20 nm was applied before imaging in the resolution range from 1 k to 5 k.

Results and discussion

Sulfonation of PPO :

PPO is a hydrophobic thermoplastic and, as such, is not suitable for preparing ion-exchange membranes without modification. Fig. 1 shows the sulfonation reaction of PPO dissolved in chloroform with chlorosulfonic acid. The incorporation of sulfonic acid groups may be carried out to yield a hydrophilic polymer. This was achieved here by reaction with chlorosulfonic acid after dissolution in chloroform. The reaction was then easily carried out at room temperature. The precipitate appeared after a certain amount of chlorosulfonic acid solution had been slowly added dropwise. The rate of addition and strength of acid affected the amount and time needed for precipitation, and caused differences in degree of sulfonation. Therefore sPPO samples obtained from various reaction baths were mixed together to obtain a material with an average value for the degree of sulfonation.

The sulfonation reaction between PPO and ClSO₃H is shown in Fig. 2(A). The presence of the -SO₃H group attached to the aromatic ring of PPO was confirmed by an FTIR peak at 1060 cm⁻¹²⁴ and ¹H NMR studies.

¹H NMR spectra were also recorded to confirm the sulfonation of PPO (Fig. 3). For PPO the characteristic chemical shifts are located at about 2.2 ppm and 6.5 ppm, which are assigned to the methyl group proton and the aromatic proton respectively. The presence of the sulfonic acid group in PPO results in the movement of the chemical shift downfield due to the strong inductive effect of -SO₃H²⁵.

Membrane casting :

Dimethylacetamide (DMAc) is a suitable solvent as it dissolves both sPPO and PVA. The 5% solution of PVA in DMAc was suitable to blend with the requisite amount

Fig. 1. Sulfonation reaction of PPO dissolved in chloroform with chlorosulfonic acid.

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Fig. 2(A). FTIR of PPO, sPPO and sPPO-PVA membrane material.

that of sPPO with equal concentration. The formed membranes were uniform and no phase separations were found. This confirmed that the PVA had been well cross-linked with glutaraldehyde and sPPO.

Cross-linking reaction :

PVA is a water soluble polymer while sPPO was insoluble in water at the extent of the sulfonation carried out. To prepare a hydrophilic but water insoluble membrane by blending sPPO with PVA, a cross-linking step via covalent bonding was adopted. Cross-linking interconnected the polymer chains of PVA through a cross-linking agent (glutaraldehyde) in the presence of an acid catalyst (sulfuric acid).

Fig. 3 shows the chemical reaction in which the formation of a lactone ring between the -OH of PVA and the -CHO of GA occurred in the presence of an acid catalyst.

Fig. 2(B). ^1H NMR of sPPO.

of sPPO solution in DMAc. During dissolution with stirring, there was a tendency for air bubbles to form, so their complete removal before casting the membrane was necessary therefore, if required, the casting solution was filtered through a cotton pad. About 10% (w/w) polymer concentration was suitable for the uniform spreading of casted solution. The PVA solution is more viscous than

The rate of cross-linking depends on the concentration of cross-linking agent, catalyst, and on the temperature of the reaction. We controlled the extent of the reaction by manipulating the reaction time. Too short a reaction time (less than 10 min) yielded water-unstable membranes while too long a time (above 45 min) produced brittleness in a dry membrane.

Fig. 3. Cross-linking reaction between glutaraldehyde and PVA.

Moisture and water uptake :

The moisture uptake and water uptake are shown in Figs. 4(A) and 4(B). One of the primary characteristics

Fig. 4. Effect of sPPO content on property (A) moisture uptake and (B) water uptake of membranes.

of hydrophilic membranes is their water uptake property because the water content directly affects other functional properties, especially proton conductivity and dimensional stability when in contact with water. Micro-phase structure is also dependent on water uptake. Absorbed water constructs a hydrophilic phase dispersed within hydrophobic polymer phase as viewed in SEM picture. Both sPPO and PVA are fairly hydrophilic polymers, therefore, variation in composition did not have much influence on water uptake. sPPO and PVA blended membranes with 50 : 50 composition showed the highest water uptake, while 100% sPPO membranes exhibited the least. The water uptake increased with increasing sPPO content until 50%, beyond which it decreased. The amount of water uptake was higher than that of Nafion115 (14.63%) for all compositions studied.

Ion-exchange capacity :

The density of the ion-exchange groups is expressed as the IEC and was measured as the number of milliequivalents of $-SO_3H$ per unit dry weight of polymer. IEC has a direct influence on the membrane conductivity and hence on its performance as proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cells. From the IEC point of view, sPPO was the active material in the sPPO-PVA composite (PVA was passive), and increasing content in the membrane linearly enhanced the IEC values (Fig. 5). Compared to Nafion, PVA blended membranes had more IEC but also had significantly higher water uptake, therefore water uptake per sulfonic acid group remained relatively higher in sPPO-PVA membranes. It is tempting to correlate the IEC of various blend compositions with water uptake but in our case there was no direct relationship because the blending material, PVA, also absorbed wa-

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Fig. 5. Dependence of ion-exchange capacity on sPPO content.

ter. The IEC of the PVA-sPPO 70 membrane was more when compared to the other PVA-sPPO membranes. This shows that PVA-sPPO 70 was hydrophilic in comparison to the other membranes.

Thermal stability :

Thermal stability of pure sPPO improved from 350–450 °C with the incorporation of PVA, as shown in Fig. 6. These curves show different degradation stages arising from the loss of water, thermal desulfonation, and thermal oxidation of the polymer matrix. The first weight loss occurred below 100 °C and was assigned to loss of

Fig. 6. TGA curve : sPPO and sPPO-PVA membranes.

absorbed water molecules from the membrane matrix due to the presence of water molecules in PVA. The second weight loss at 350–450 °C corresponded to the loss of sulfonic acid from the sPPO matrix. In the third weight loss region (> 450 °C), the polymer chains were degraded. It can be concluded that the introduction of PVA into the sPPO matrix improved the thermal stability of the PVA-sPPO membrane when compared to the pure sPPO membrane.

Membrane morphology :

The SEM image shows the homogeneous and porous structure of the sPPO membrane blended with PVA (Fig. 7). The image shows the absorbed water constructs hydrophilic phase dispersed in a hydrophobic polymer phase. The effect of the PVA content on the sPPO matrix is clearly reflected by cross-sectional surface images. In the sPPO-PVA membrane, porosity is due to PVA aggre-

Fig. 7. Cross sectional view of sPPO-PVA membrane.

gates while the homogeneity is due to the sPPO-PVA composite. The PVA aggregates store the water content and lead to a hydrophilic channel which connects the proton conductivity through the sulfonic acid groups of sPPO. This confirms that adding PVA into the sPPO matrix increases the hydrophilic nature in the membrane matrix which, in turn, increases the membrane conductivity when compared to the pure sPPO membrane.

Membrane resistivity :

Membrane resistance (R_m) may be calculated as,

$$R_m = R_{m+e} - R_e \left[\frac{d-l}{d} \right] \quad (4)$$

where, R_{m+e} and R_e are electrolyte resistance, with and without membrane respectively. Distance between electrodes is d and membrane thickness is l . Thus, the quantity in the parenthesis is a correction factor for electrolyte resistance, since it would be less in the case when a cell holds the membrane than that when it contains only electrolyte²⁶. The membrane conductivity (k^m) was further calculated using the following relation :

$$k^m = \frac{1}{R_m} \cdot \frac{l}{A} \quad (5)$$

where, A is the area of electrodes.

The activation energy of proton conductivity in the membrane (E_a) was found by the Arrhenius relation :

$$\ln k^m = - \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (6)$$

Diffusion coefficient of proton in membrane phase ($D_{H^+}^m$) was calculated using following relation²⁷ :

$$D_{H^+}^m = \frac{RT}{F^2} \cdot \frac{k^m}{Q} \quad (7)$$

where R is the gas constant, F is the Faraday constant, T is the absolute temperature (K) and Q is the ion-exchange capacity of the joint gel phase (mol m^{-3}) given by $Q = \text{IEC} \times \text{density of wet membrane}$ ²⁸.

In our case membrane resistance (R_m) was calculated as the impedance on the real axis of a Nyquist plot where the imaginary part was zero and remaining calculations were performed as above. Fig. 8 shows the conductivity of PVA-sPPO membranes with different temperatures. The conductivity for PVA-sPPO composite membranes was increased with temperature up to 80 °C (0.0092 S cm^{-1} for PVA-sPPO 70). This observation suggested a temperature assisted proton transport phenomena in the PVA-sPPO 70 membrane. These results suggested that the PVA-sPPO 70 membrane could be a promising candidate for high temperature application under anhydrous conditions such as PEMFC.

The activation energy and diffusivity calculated from conductivity data are given in Tables 1 and 2. All membranes exhibited positive temperature-conductivity dependencies, which suggested a thermally activated conduc-

Fig. 8. Change of membrane conductivity with temperature.

tion process under an experimental temperature range (30–80 °C). Fig. 9 shows the activation energy of PVA-sPPO membranes. The E_a values increased with the PVA content in the membrane matrix and ranged between 3.4 and 3.9 kJ mol^{-1} (Table 1). At a higher temperature, fast proton and water molecule diffusion take place resulting in a rapid conduction process, due to a more continuous pathway because of interconnected hydrophilic channels²⁹. In general the activation energy indicates the amount of energy required to break a hydrogen bond in water. The activation energy PVA-sPPO 70 membrane was high which indicates that high proton conductivity of the membrane. Proton transport in Nafion membranes was dominated by the Grotthuss mechanism³⁰. This indicated that in the sPPO-PVA 70 membrane the transport of ions was due to the Grotthuss mechanism, and that hydrogen bonding has taken place between the hydroxyl groups of PVA and the sPPO in the membrane.

Membrane potentials and transport number :

Transport number, t_{+}^m , was calculated by the measurement of membrane potentials (E^m) on the basis of

Table 1. Activation energies of sPPO-PVA membranes calculated from Arrhenius plot

Membrane (% of sPPO)	Slope of Arrhenius plot	Activation energy (kJ/mol)
30	-0.41909	3.4834761
40	-0.43047	3.5780666
50	-0.42404	3.5246205
60	-0.47936	3.9544403
70	-0.47618	3.9880082
Solution N/40 H ₂ SO ₄	-0.38827	3.2273002

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Table 2. Proton diffusion coefficient of sPPO-PVA membranes

% sPPO	Temperature (°C)		Diffusivity (m ² /s)			
	30	40	50	60	70	80
30	1.90088E-10	2.08726E-10	2.2373E-10	2.39619E-10	2.51E-10	2.73E-10
40	1.43097E-10	1.51986E-10	1.5778E-10	1.63914E-10	1.69E-10	1.76E-10
50	1.09028E-10	1.15649E-10	1.2086E-10	1.24782E-10	1.29E-10	1.34E-10
60	8.8242E-11	9.30931E-11	9.8246E-11	1.01051E-10	1.04E-10	1.12E-10
70	9.18431E-11	9.90027E-11	1.023E-10	1.04855E-10	1.09E-10	1.18E-10
Solution N/40 H ₂ SO ₄	7.37397E-09	7.76978E-09	7.8742E-09	8.09245E-09	8.48E-09	8.99E-09

Fig. 9. Arrhenius plot of conductivity of membranes.

Toreal, Meyer and Sievers (TMS) Theory using following equation³¹.

$$E^m = (2t_+^m - 1) \frac{RT}{F} \ln \left(\frac{a_1}{a_2} \right) \quad (8)$$

where R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature in Kelvin, F is the Faraday constant, and a_1 and a_2 are the activities of the electrolyte solutions (HCl).

Fig. 10 shows the membrane potential of PVA-sPPO membranes. When the membrane was subjected to various driving forces such as gradients of electric potential, concentration, hydrostatic pressure, a variety of transport phenomena took place through the membrane. The membrane potential for PVA-sPPO 70 membrane was 57 mV at 0.00625 N HCl which indicates that the transport of ions was very good due to the high potential generated at the surface of the membrane.

The transport numbers of the PVA-sPPO membranes are shown in Fig. 11. Examination of the transport numbers for H⁺ in the membrane phase revealed that PVA-

Fig. 10. Variation of membrane potential with sPPO content.

sPPO membranes exhibited good transport number. The transport number of the PVA-sPPO 70 membrane further increased with the concentration of PVA in the membrane matrix and the transport number was 0.97 when compared to other PVA-sPPO membranes.

Fig. 11. Variation of membrane transport number with electrolyte concentration.

Conclusions

A series of PVA-sPPO membranes with different percentages of PVA and sPPO ranging from 30% to 70% were prepared. The structure of PVA-sPPO membranes were confirmed by FTIR and proton NMR. The water uptake of PVA-sPPO increased with an increase in the sulfonation and temperature. The water content of the PVA-sPPO 70 was higher than that of the other PVA-sPPO membranes. TGA showed the sulfonic groups attached to the aromatic ring in the sPPO backbone decomposed at the stage of 350–400 °C, but the main-chain splitting temperature of PVA-sPPO 70 was similar to that of the pure polymer. SEM images showed the membrane porous was due to PVA aggregates while the homogeneity was due to the sPPO-PVA composite. The conductivity of the sPPO-PVA at higher temperature was very good, which suggests that the membrane could be used in high temperature applications. This result was also strengthened by the values of membrane potential and transport number, where sPPO-PVA 70 exhibited highly favourable properties when compared to other sPPO-PVA membranes. In conclusion, the sPPO-PVA 70 membrane could be used for various membrane applications including fuel cells and electrodialysis.

Acknowledgement

The author (PKB) gratefully acknowledges the financial support received from ISRO; vide sponsored project sanction letter number STC/CHE/2015116. RKN thanks the Department of Science & Technology (DST), Government of India, for Ramanujan Fellowship (SR/S2/RJN-18/2011) award and financial support (Grant Number SR/S3/CE/034/2013).

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